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CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS OF INTEGRATING EMERGING OFFICE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUSINESS EDUCATION IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

Oghenekaro Juliet Asemota, Chukwudumebi Emmanuel Nwabuoku and Adaeze Blessing Okonkwo

Department of Accounting Education,
School of Secondary Education
(Business), Federal College of Education
(Technical), Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria.
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Abstract: The study investigated the emerging office technologies and challenges in the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. Two research questions and hypotheses were raised in line with the purpose of the study. The research design adopted for the study was descriptive survey. The population comprised of 175 Business education lecturers across all tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. The sample consisted of the 175 Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. The rationale for using the entire population is because the researcher considered it small and manageable. The instruments used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. In order to determine the validity, the instrument was given to three experts in the department of Vocational and Technical Education, Faculty of Education, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, their corrections were incorporated in the final instrument. The instrument yielded a reliability result of 0.74 by employing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) to measure the degree of consistency, this showed that the instrument was reliable. The data collected from the field were analyzed using mean, standard deviation for research questions while t-test statistical tools was used to analyze the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that change in office technology is posing a lot of challenges to the delivery of Business education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. Findings revealed that emerging office technologies are not available in the delivery of business education programme in tertiary institutions South-South Nigeria and changes in office technology pose a lot of challenges to the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria among others. It was recommended that retraining programmes should be intensified for all trainable instructional personnel also, a separate statutory or budgetary allocation should be made for the provision or updating of relevant office technologies for Business education among others.

Keywords: South-South Nigeria, Tertiary Institutions and Business Education.

Introduction

The world today is passing through lots of changes in schools, offices, industries and virtually every facet of human endeavour. The changes are no doubt, noticed more in science and technology which has restructured office functions and also ushered in the teaching and learning of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in schools, especially in Office Technology and Management (OTM) programmes in higher institutions in Nigeria

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(Oyagiri & Ekoh 2013). This has confirmed the words of McLuhan (1980) that the world was going to become a global village. In line with this, Idogho (2013) asserted that the emerging technologies have shrunk the five or six continent worlds into a “global village” in which people can interact, transact business, source for information and carry out limitless operations that reach across the globe, at mind boggling speed and fidelity. These office technologies are indications that the global work environment is changing, therefore, the skills required by the workforce now is growing in complexity compared to years back. This change is due to the dynamic nature of technology which cuts across all facet of life. Offices are now equipped with more sophisticated technological gadgets which need special skills to be manipulated. In the present world, the stock and flow of knowledge available to individuals, organizations and nations, determine their competitive position and level of performance and sustainability. As such, in order to remain relevant in the dynamic society, teachers, students and workers in the field of business have to keep up with the pace of change. To be equipped with the skills required to be active in the present business environment, there is need for prospective business educators to pass through a course of study in which the content and learning experiences are programmed to shape students to be useful and productive in the global business environment. The course of study that matches this task is Business Education.

Business Education as defined by Adesina (2007) is a programme that prepares students for entry into and advancement in job within business. In line with this, Wikipedia (2013) also defined Business Education as the teaching of students the fundamentals, theories and process of business. Traditionally, Business Education is aimed at equipping students with skills in keyboarding, office procedures or filing system, book-keeping, commerce or marketing skills, but with the changes in the world of business today, brought about by the emerging office technologies, most of these skills are becoming obsolete. Since Business Education is aimed at providing students with skills that will enable them strive in business, its curriculum should be flexible enough to reflect the dynamic nature of office technology which is the heart of the modern day business offices. With the frequent changes in office technology, the concept of curriculum review is of utmost importance. Curriculum, from its original Latin meaning, means “running a course” or a course which one runs to reach a goal (Alaba, 2011). This means that curriculum has to do with the planning of a particular course that the learners have to undergo to achieve specific level of knowledge in any field of education. Curriculum as defined by Bentley (2013) refers to the means and materials with which students will interact for the purpose of achieving identified educational outcomes. If this be the case, business education curriculum can be said to include all learning experiences designed for students to achieve the planned objectives of Business education and the means (media, methods, personnel) with which the learning will be done. Business educators who have the primary responsibility of equipping students with the relevant skills, knowledge and attitude which they need to become employable and productive in the business world are likely to be confronted with myriad of challenges in keeping abreast with technological developments that have completely altered the operational landscape that they were used to (Agbonifoh, 2013).

One major challenge of the emerging technologies to Business Education is that advances in technology challenges the very essence of Business Education as currently narrowly conceived. A major question which business educators need to answer is whether the current philosophy of Business Education is still relevant or appropriate, considering the major changes that have taken place in the way business organizations now operate. Traditionally, business education would seem to have focused on equipping non managerial workers with basic skills required for

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providing clerical and secretarial services in the work place especially in business organizations in today's world. Development in technology, especially information and communication technology, have almost totally eroded the need for workers with these skills. The growing trends in business now encourage multi-skilling and multi-tasking both of which require individual workers to have multiple skills so as to be able to perform multiple tasks. For example, all white collar workers, especially managers in world class organizations today require and many do have keyboarding skills. They have their laptops to perform many tasks on their own, thereby reducing the demand for Business Education graduates in modern businesses except in the classroom. The question that comes to mind here is whether or not this calls for a revisit of the philosophical foundations of Business Education. Although business educators are actually being trained for teaching positions in various institutions, it should also be noted that the classroom experience is not an end in itself, it is the utilization of the skills learnt by students in the actual world of work that matters. That is to say the actual practicalisation of these skills in the present-day business office is declining due to the frequent advancements in office technology. This is not to say that Business Education skills are no longer relevant but that the philosophy, scope, objectives and content of Business Education programme as practiced today need to change to reflect the present and future technological advancements.

Government over all attitudes towards education in Nigeria is poor and this is also militating against effective implementation of the new office technologies in business education. Education gets one of the poorest allocations in the national budget, teachers are constantly humiliated by students, parents and employers and they are the least paid professionals in Nigeria (Agbonifoh 2013). With such degrading treatment, teaching is not made an attractive occupation. Students do not go to school to study education courses willingly but most times as the only alternative left after trying to go into other fields. With such challenge, the required technological input may not be made available in education programmes, one of which is business education. The change in technology has been an ongoing event. Over the years, some initiatives have been made as the world keeps improving in technology, to bridge the gap between school experience and actual work experience. One of these initiatives is the introduction of students Industrial Training (IT). In this scheme, students are compulsorily sent out of the school environment to be attached to firms or other real life working environments, for them to acquire the practical experience of the skills they are being taught in the class room. With this, students are made to acquire firsthand experience of what they have been taught while still in school. Another initiative is the introduction of Teaching Practice (TP). Teaching practice is a scheme designed for students to practice the teaching skills they have been thought in an organised school setting. After a period of learning and observing of the more experienced teachers, the student teachers are evaluated from a life performance and graded accordingly. Other initiatives that have been brought up to bridge the gap between class room experience and the actual work experience include; practical classroom drills, team teaching, assignments, projects, in-service training, entrepreneurship education and the likes. Even with the introduction of student Industrial Training into the tertiary institutions, there still exists a vacuum as a result of the frequent change in technology in the business environment.

It can be said that the present Business Education curriculum is made up more of manual skills. The manual skills being taught in Business Education are important because they give students a thorough understanding of the principles behind the business activities they are being taught and also give students the required background to learning and understanding the skills demanded by the automated or electronic devices in the present business

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environment. This fact notwithstanding, the place of the utilization of the manual or traditional business skills, is slim in the present business environment. According to Marsan (2009) the top ten technological skills required to thrive in the modern business environment include; business process skills which represent an understanding of how the business operates and the ability to predict the impact of a particular decision or action on the rest of the enterprise, database skills, which enable one to manipulate data to get meaningful information, messaging/communication skills which involve the tactful use of the means of communication in business to send the required message to the clients of a business enterprise, IT architecture skills which are used to denote a variety of IT domains, IT security skills which involves the installation, configuration, upgrading, network monitoring, implementing secure computer systems, responding to successful attacks with the appropriate countermeasures and so on, project management skills which involve the designing, monitoring analyzing, implementing and evaluating projects, data mining skills which involve the process of analyzing data from different perspectives and summarizing them into useful information, web development skills which require one to get a sound knowledge of computer operation, remote access, file uploading and downloading, HTML and XHTML and so on, IT optimization skills and networking skills. Therefore, more attention has to be given to the inculcation of these skills for a better implementation of the emerging office technologies in Business education.

Statement of the Problem

The content of Business Education curriculum as presently offered in tertiary institutions in Nigeria, includes Accounting, Secretarial Studies or Office Information Technology, keyboarding, Commerce, Marketing, Shorthand and Business Management. These contents are good but the learning experiences allotted to them by the schools seem not to match with the requirements of the present business environment. While the learning experiences students are exposed to in school is mostly based on manual business skills such as Shorthand, Typewriting, paper filing and Book keeping, the actual work environment demands people who are skillful in manipulating the emerging electronic or automated office devices or facilities. This is because the electronic or automated devices are faster, more convenient and in the long run, cheaper than the manual devices, so the electronic devices are more preferable by modern business owners. Idogho (2013), pointed out that there are now new, better, more efficient and cheaper ways of doing things which unarguably have serious implications on the theory and practice of Business Education. The dynamic nature of office technology is so obvious because in less than two decades ago, a modern office was stocked with; typewriter, cyclostyling machines, facsimile, file cabinet, telephone land lines. Today, computer with the internet has taken over and drastically reduced the clumsiness of the ideal office. The new technologies operate with innumerable applications and software which make possible data management and transfer, e-banking, commerce as well as social networks with technology mediated interaction sites such as Facebook, Skype, Blog.

The problem here, which is the reason for this study, is that presently, Business Education curriculum, its philosophy, scope and contents seem not to be changing in the pace with which the business environment is changing due to the emerging office technologies. Utoware and Amiaya (2014) opined that the restructuring of business education curriculum to adapt with these changes in the society, is seen as the evidence of the impact of the new technologies. They went further to add that it is the curriculum that conveys the environment for effective and efficient realization of technology impartation and adaptation on the part of business educators. The current

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course outline in the faculty handbooks of Delta State university, Nnamdi Azikiwe university, Akwa, the National Diploma (ND) and Higher National Diploma (FIND) course analyses by NBTE highlights courses such as office information system, modern office technologies, computer programming, data base management skills, data processing, ICT office application, advance web page design, desktop publishing and many other technologically based courses.

The problem lies greatly in the learning experience. This is because the learning materials (technologies), human resource and practical work experience are not available to match the courses outlined. Students learn in abstract without practical which are the most important method of teaching and learning technological based courses. The result of this is that student graduate with obsolete skills which will not enable them to function relevantly in the modern business offices which are characterized with new office technologies. If the curriculum planners as well as the management of schools that offer Business Education do not find ways to make the curriculum as well as its implementation, flexible enough to always be in line with the trend of change in office technology, the field of study may soon become obsolete and irrelevant to the society and this may lead to its eviction from the school system and unemployment for those who have built a career in the field. Since this is the case, are Business Education lecturers aware of the emerging technologies, the skills required to implement these office technologies and the challenges they pose to Business Education and its stakeholders? If yes, what initiatives are they employing in delivering Business Education programmes in the midst of these challenges?

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the emerging office technologies and challenges in the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. This study sought to find out:

1. The extent to which the new office technologies are available for the delivery of Business Education program in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.
2. The extent to which the frequent changes in office technologies pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education program in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. **Research Questions**

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are the emerging office technologies available in the delivery of business education programme in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria?
2. To what extent do the frequent changes in office technology pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria? **Hypotheses**

The following null hypotheses was tested at 0.05, level of significance;

1. There is no significant difference in the opinion of Universities and Colleges of Education/Polytechnics Business Education lecturers on extent to which the new office technologies are available for the delivery of Business Education program in South-South Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the opinion of Universities and Colleges of Education/Polytechnics Business Education lecturers on extent to which the frequent changes in office technologies pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education program in South-South Nigeria.

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Scope of the Study

This study investigates the emerging office technologies, the challenges posed by the emerging office technologies to Business Education, the skills needed for the implementation of the emerging office technologies in Business Education, the initiatives of Lecturers in the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in Delta and Edo states, and possible solutions to the challenges posed by the emerging office technologies to Business Education. This study involves Business Education Lecturers from eight higher institutions that offer Business Education and office Technology and Management.

Methodology

Descriptive survey was used as the design for this study. Survey research according to Nworgu (2006) is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only few persons considered to be representative of the entire population. This research design is suitable for this study because it is intended to collect and analyze data from business education lecturers who represent the entire population that are being faced by the challenges of the emerging office technologies and whose initiatives are being used to manage these challenges. The population of the study comprised of all Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. Information from Deans office from various institutions stated that, there are 175 Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. The table below shows the distributions.

Table 1: Distribution of the Population of Business Education Lecturers by institutions

<u>S/N</u>	<u>Name of Institutions</u>	<u>Population</u>
1	Ambrose Ali University, Ekpoma	08
2	Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi	08
3	College of Education Warri, Delta State	18
4	Delta State Polytechnic, Oghara	10
5	Delta State University Abraka	16
6	Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba	71
7	Federal College of Education Technical, Ekiadolor	04
8	University of Benin, Benin City	16
9	University of Delta, Agbor	17
10	University of Science and Technology, Ozoro.	07
Total		175

The sample consisted of the 175 Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in SouthSouth Nigeria. The rationale for using the entire population is because the researcher considered it small and manageable. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. It was titled Emerging office technologies and challenges questionnaire (EOTCQ). The questionnaire was made up of two parts; A and B. Part A elicited information on personal data from respondents while part B contained items for answering the two research questions. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point scale with responses ranging from Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). To determine the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire subjected to face and content validity of three experts in the Department of Vocational

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and Technical Education, Faculty of Education, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State. They were requested to vet the items for appropriateness and ambiguity. Their recommendations and corrections were adhered to which enhanced face and content validity of the instrument. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument a pilot study was conducted. The instrument was administered to 20 Business education lecturers in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to determine the internal consistency of the items in the instruments. Hence, a reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained which indicated that the instrument was reliable.

Validated copies of the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents by the researcher and two experienced research assistants. The research assistants were assigned to administer the instrument to business education lecturers. The administered instrument was retrieved the same day it was administered which ensures a 100% return rate. Out of the 175 instruments, only 169 was distributed and retrieved because as at the period of distribution, 6 respondents could not be reached. Data collected was used for data analysis. To analyze the data collected, mean, standard deviation, t-test was used. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was based on any calculated mean equal or greater than 2.50 was regarded as high extent while any mean lesser than 2.50 was regarded as low extent. On the bases of hypothesis, the probability (p) was used. If p -value is less than or equal to 0.05 H_0 was rejected but if p -value is greater than 0.05, H_0 was retained.

Results

Data Analysis for Research Question

Research Question 1: To what extent are the emerging office technologies available in the delivery of business education programme in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.

S/N	Items	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	\bar{x}	S.D	Decision
1	Tablets Pcs	15	24	70	60	1.97	0.92	Low Extent

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation response on the emerging office technologies available in the delivery of business education programme in tertiary institutions (N = 169)

2	Jaw Bone Icon	13	12	79	65	1.84	0.86	Low Extent
3	18 button computer mouse	24	20	65	60	2.05	1.01	Low Extent
4	Dictating machine	29	30	50	60	2.17	1.09	Low Extent
5	PowerPoint	72	70	14	13	3.18	0.89	High Extent
6	Microsoft office vision	12	11	82	64	1.83	0.84	Low Extent
7	Microsoft Office Access	85	71	10	3	3.41	0.79	High Extent
8	3D Printer	22	21	62	64	2.01	1.01	Low Extent
9	Microsoft Optical Character Recognition.	24	20	65	60	2.05	1.01	Low Extent
10	Digital Paper Prototype	29	10	70	60	2.04	1.04	Low Extent
11	Automated Teller Machine	10	3	85	71	1.72	0.77	Low Extent
12	Stationed Security Access Gadgets	14	13	72	70	1.83	0.89	Low Extent
13	Peach Tree Accounting Software	15	24	70	60	1.96	0.92	Low Extent

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14	Blog	13	12	79	65	1.84	0.86	Low	Extent				
15	Skype	11	7	80	71	1.75	0.81	Low	Extent				
16	Microsoft xbox			19	10	90	50	1.99	0.89	Low	Extent		
17	Skye Drive	14	10	73	72	1.79	0.89	Low	Extent				
18	Minuscule Adjustick Cell Phone			24	20	65	60	2.04	1.01	Low	Extent		
19	Webcam	44	12	58	55	2.27	1.17	Low	Extent				
20	Trunked Mobile Radio			24	14	68	63	1.99	1.01	Low	Extent		
21	Router	25	15	79	50	2.09	0.98	Low	Extent				
22	Palm Pilot	24	20	65	60	2.05	1.01	Low	Extent				
23	Microsoft Excel			14	10	75	70	1.81	0.88	Low	Extent		
24	E-Reader	14	10	73	72	1.79	0.88	Low	Extent				
25	Microsoft Word			13	12	79	65	1.84	0.86	Low	Extent		
26	Optical Mark Reader	14	13	72	70	1.83	0.89	Low	Extent				
27	Interactive					19	10	80	60	1.93	0.93	Low	Extent
28	Alliance promotion video card					10	3	85	71	1.95	0.89	Low	Extent
Grand Mean								2.03	Low	Extent			

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Result presented in Table 2 reveals the emerging office technologies available in the delivery of business education programme in tertiary institutions. The result revealed that the items 1 to 3, 6, and 8 to 28 scored lesser than the decision-making mean of 2.50 this indicated low extent. Items 5 and 7 were rated above 2.50 which indicated high extent. Standard deviation scores range between 0.77 to 1.17 were obtained indicating close spread of respondents' opinion ratings. The grand mean score of 2.03 which is below the decision-making mean of 2.50 confirms that respondents rated low extent, this indicated that emerging office technologies are not available in the delivery of business education programme in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.

Research Question 2: To what extent do the frequent changes in office technology pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Response on frequent changes in office technology pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions (N = 169)

SN	Items	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	\bar{x}	SD	Remark		
29	The technological changes in the actual workplace are too frequent for schools to adapt easily	73	72	14	10	3.23	0.84	High	Extent	
30	High cost of training and retraining of personnel to meet the technological changes in office technology pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria	85	71	10	3	3.41	0.68	High	Extent	
31	Insufficient fund to acquire the office technological	72	70	14	13	3.19	0.89	High	Extent	emerging

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32	facilities for schools' instruction	Poor interest in continuous self development on the part of lecturers	65	60	24	20	3.01	1.00	High Extent
33	students during industrial work experience.	Poor follow-up supervision of	75	70	14	10	3.24	0.84	High Extent
34	lecturer in manipulating the emerging office technologies	Lack of requisites skills on the part of	80	60	19	10	3.24	0.88	High Extent
35	for the number of students in schools are too poor for effective instruction	The teachers and equipment available	79	65	13	12	3.25	0.88	High Extent

Grand Mean	3.22	High Extent
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Source: Field Survey, 2024

Result presented in Table 3 reveals the frequent changes in office technology pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions. The result revealed that the items 29 to 35 scored above the decision-making mean of 2.50 this indicated high extent. Standard deviation scores range between 0.68 to 1.00 were obtained indicating close spread of respondents' opinion ratings. The grand mean score of 3.22 which is above the decision-making mean of 2.50 confirms that respondents rated high extent, which means that changes in office technology pose a lot of challenges to the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.

Testing of the Hypotheses

The data analyses for testing the hypotheses were carried out using T-test.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the opinion of Universities and Colleges of Education/Polytechnics Business Education lecturers on extent to which the new office technologies are available for the delivery of Business Education program in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.

Table 4: T-test analysis lecturers' opinions on extent to which the new office technologies are available for the delivery of Business Education program in tertiary institutions.

Lecturers	N	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Universities	64	3.37	0.75	249	0.04	1.96 Do not reject
Colleges of Education1/Polytechnics	105	3.34	0.68			

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4 reveals that the calculated t-tables at 0.05 level of significance and 249 degree of freedom was 0.04; while critical t-value under the same conditions was 1.96. Since the calculated t-value was less than the table-value, the null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that lecturers in universities and colleges of education/polytechnics do not differ in their opinion of the extent to which the new office technologies are available for the delivery of business education programme in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria is retrained.

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Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the opinion of Universities and Colleges of Education/Polytechnics Business Education lecturers on extent to which the frequent changes in office technologies pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education program in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.

Table 5: T-test analysis lecturers’ opinions on extent to which frequent changes in office technologies pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education program in tertiary institutions.

Lecturers	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Universities	64	3.25	0.79	249	1.11	1.96	Do not reject
Colleges of Education/Polytechnics	105	3.24	0.82				

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 5 showed that the calculated t-table at 0.05 level of significance and 249 degree of freedom was 1.11; while the critical t-value under the same conditions was 1.96. Since the calculated was less than the Table value the null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that lecturers in universities and colleges of education/polytechnics do not differ in their opinion of the extent to which the frequent changes in office technologies pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education program in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria is retained.

Discussion of Results

The findings from research question one revealed that emerging office technologies are not available in the delivery of business education programme in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. The hypothesis one also states that lecturers in universities and colleges of education/polytechnics do not differ in their opinion of the extent to which the new office technologies are available for the delivery of business education programme in South-South Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with that of Eze (2008) who opined that certain facilities are specially designed to enhance the teaching of skills in Office Technology and Management (OTM), without which such skills cannot be acquired. He added that it is very disturbing that the tertiary institutions are retarded in terms of technological equipment, modern offices and functional laboratories. Ikpe and Undie (2014) also posited that Business education like other phase of Vocational and Technical Education require the use of modern office technologies in the process of preparing 21st century office workers and that these technologies are lacking in the system.

The findings from research question two revealed that changes in office technology pose a lot of challenges to the delivery of Business Education in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. While the hypotheses revealed that lecturers in universities and colleges of education/polytechnics do not differ in their opinion of the extent to which the frequent changes in office technologies pose a challenge to the delivery of Business Education program in tertiary institutions in South-

South Nigeria. Ike (2008) is in agreement with this finding when he posited that the implementation of the curriculum of Office Technology and Management (OTM) in Nigeria is faced with the challenges of provision of sufficient fund, inadequate attention and sponsorship by the government due to lack of fund. This according to him is due to the fact that the new curriculum of OTM has made it more capital intensive.

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Conclusion

The findings of this study have indeed revealed that the emerging office technologies has posed great challenges to Business education due to the fact that tertiary institutions are not able to move at the same pace with which these office technologies are changing by not being able to make available these new office technologies for the delivery of Business education programme. This has created a gap between the school instructional process and the real work environment. The modern technological skills demanded by the modern business offices are not being adequately inculcated into the students who are expected to work in the modern offices. From one of the findings of this study which states that to a large extent lecturers are using the initiatives of practical work experience in the delivery of Business education, one can deduce that the practical work experiences are not been done effectively enough to bridge the gap between the school system and the real world of work and this is as a result of the challenges mentioned in the study. The researcher concluded that apart from the unavailability of the new office technologies for the delivery of Business education, the practical work experience initiatives which could have helped to a large extent in bridging the gap is failing due to problems such as; lack of adequate supervision of students during industrial work attachment period; lack of follow up by those involved in the training process; wrong placement of student during industrial training (that is, allowing students to have their industrial training in establishments that cannot provide them with the needed specialization); poor interest and unseriousness of students during industrial training and so on. Also, the results of this findings of this research cannot be generalized to the South-South States but Delta and Edo States which was the focus of the research.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- a. Retraining programmes should be intensified for all trainable instructional personnel.
- b. A separate statutory or budgetary allocation should be made for the provision or updating of relevant office technologies for Business education.
- c. A team of experts should be set-up by Association of Business Educators of Nigeria (ABEN) to liaise with relevant statutory agencies of government to review the curriculum of Business education at all levels.
- d. All training institutions should ensure that their proprietors (government or private) provide the relevant and state-of-arts technologies for the preparation of Business education students to meet up with the 21st century administrative business office environment.
- e. Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) should be intensified with well monitored supervision schedule and follow-up.
- f. A regular business office survey should be carried out by the curriculum planners and lecturers of Business education to get the awareness of the latest office technologies in use. This will enable them pass on current knowledge to their students.
- g. Experts should be employed to anchor the practical teaching of the modern office technology skills in schools with the required office technologies.
- h. Regular seminars should be organized for business educators that will help them to get the awareness of the skills required to manipulate the office technologies in modern business offices and also encourage them to upgrade their teaching skills.

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